

and low total N (0.34%). Available P was 11-13 ppm (Olsen's method).

P rates did not affect the rice yields significantly (see table). In the second year, higher yields of transplanted rice were attributed to short and good

stand, synchronized ripening, lower sterility, and lower weed density.

The results showed that barley could follow transplanted rice. The yields of rice - barley were close to those of the main crops grown by local farmers. $\mathcal{L}$

replications. The soil was medium black, fertilized with 25 kg N and 22 kg P/ha at sowing the last week of December and irrigated every 10-12 d with 50 mm of water at each of 10 irrigations.

Shulamith yielded significantly more dry pods than TG-1 and Kopargaon-1 (see table). SB-11 had the highest oil content. Spacing at 30 × 15 cm yielded significantly more dry pods, SB-11 at 30 × 15 cm produced the highest dry pod yield. $\mathcal{L}$

High productivity varietal combinations in a rice - wheat rotation in Chhattisgarh, India

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The Chhattisgarh area of Madhya Pradesh is a slightly moist hot zone with a moisture index between -20 and 0, and a mean annual temperature between 25° C and 18° C. Annual rainfall ranges from 1,000 to 1,500 mm, mostly concentrated in Jun-Sep. Soil type represents the red-yellow group, clay loam to clay. Rice, the principal crop, is grown mainly during the monsoon season, followed by linseed, lathyrus, urid, moong, gram, rape, mustard, and groundnut. Wheat is a recent second-crop introduction.

A 3-yr experiment to find the best varietal combination for high productivity in a rice - wheat rotation was initiated during 1978 kharif. Early, medium, and late duration rice varieties were followed by early, medium, and late duration wheat varieties in all combinations. Rice varieties were J.R.16-15-1-1 (90-100 d), Ratna (120-125 d), and Jaya (130-135 d). Wheat varieties were Sonalika (110 d), Jairaj (115 d), and K. Sona (125 d).

The experiment was a randomized block design with nine treatment combinations and four replications.

Effect of planting method on grain yield of 2 rice cultivars in Çorum, Turkey.^a

P rate (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)					
	Direct seeded			Transplanted		
	1983	1984	Mean	1983	1984	Mean
	<i>Ribe</i>					
0	7.2	3.2	5.2	5.5	4.5	5.0
18	7.4	2.8	5.1	5.5	3.8	4.6
35	6.9	3.2	5.1	5.5	4.3	4.9
53	7.3	3.2	5.3	6.0	4.3	5.2
Mean	7.2	3.1	5.2	5.6	4.2	4.9
	<i>Krasnodarsky 424</i>					
0	9.3	5.9	7.6	6.9	6.5	6.7
18	9.1	5.9	7.5	6.9	6.9	6.9
35	9.6	5.6	7.6	6.7	6.8	6.8
53	10.3	6.3	8.3	6.8	7.2	7.0
Mean	9.6	5.9	7.8	6.7	6.9	6.8

^aIn both planting methods and years: P rates - ns, CV (%) - 8.54 in 1983, 10.20 in 1984, P × cultivar - ns, CV (%) - 6.11 in 1983, 6.71 in 1984.

Irrigated peanut following rice in Konkan, India

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In Konkan, a humid area with heavy monsoon rainfall (3,000-3,500 mm a year), rice has been a single Jun-Oct crop. Introduction of irrigation in the

dry season has created opportunities for double cropping.

We evaluated peanut varieties and optimal spacing. The legume oil seed crop has high market value in the area.

Combinations of five peanut varieties (TG-1, M-13, Shulamith, SB-11, and Kopargaon-1) with 115-120 d maturity and 3 spacings (30 × 15, 45 × 15, and 30 × 30 cm) were evaluated in a randomized block design with 3

Dry pod yield of peanut varieties and plant spacing.^a Konkan, India.

Variety	Dry pod yield (t/ha)			Mean yield (t/ha)	Oil (%)
	30 × 15 cm	45 × 15 cm	30 × 30 cm		
TG-1	2.7	2.9	2.7	2.8	47.8
M-13	3.1	2.9	2.8	2.9	48.3
Shulamith	3.4	3.3	2.5	3.1	46.2
SB-11	3.6	2.6	2.5	2.9	51.4
Kopargaon-1	2.4	2.5	2.4	2.4	48.8
Mean	3.1	2.8	2.6	-	-
	CD at 5%				
		Variety	0.2		
		Spacing	0.2		
		Variety × Spacing	0.4		

^a1978-80 pooled averages.

Each crop was supplied 120 kg N, 26 kg P, and 50 kg K/ha. Productivity was highest with Ratna,

a medium duration rice, followed by Sonalika, an early duration wheat (see table). The next best varietal

combination was Jaya rice followed by Sonalika. Medium and late wheat varieties did not perform well. *ℳ*

Productivity of varietal combinations in rice - wheat rotations. Chhatisgarh, India.

Rice	Yield (t/ha)			Mean	Wheat	Yield (t/ha)			Mean
	1977-78	1978-79	1979-80			1977-78	1978-79	1979-80	
J.R.16-15-1 (early)	5.05	3.99	5.34	4.79	Sonalika (early)	4.13	3.63	2.81	3.52
	5.03	3.80	5.05	4.63	K. Sona (late)	3.77	0.72	2.25	2.25
	4.91	4.05	5.11	4.69	Jairaj (medium)	2.93	0.56	1.75	1.75
Ratna (medium)	4.81	6.51	5.24	5.52	Sonalika	4.73	3.66	4.19	4.19
	5.11	5.94	5.12	5.39	K. Sona	4.23	0.88	2.56	2.89
	5.02	4.95	5.12	5.03	Jairaj	3.59	0.38	1.98	1.98
Jaya (late)	5.75	4.95	5.49	5.39	Sonalika	3.74	3.68	3.71	3.71
	5.79	5.56	5.19	5.51	K. Sona	3.91	1.01	2.46	2.46
	5.97	6.36	5.52	5.95	Jairaj	2.76	0.87	1.82	1.82

Announcements

Reorganized GEU rice team in Taiwan

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Rice breeding in Taiwan was reorganized in 1985. Major modifications are: 1) A rice breeding team consisting of all District Agricultural Improvement Stations (DAIS) and scientists of several disciplines at TARI and Chiayi Agricultural Experiment Station (AES)/TARI, a project led by a senior rice breeder of TARI; 2) TARI and Chiayi AES/TARI responsible for germplasm conservation, crossing, and handling of hybrid materials up to establishment of strains; 3) DAIS test for specified traits of lines or strains and undertake yield trials and culture method tests; 4) Taichung DAIS responsible for indica rice breeding; and promising strains are tested for yield only at Taichung, Tainan, and Kaoshiung DAIS; 5) new varieties identified by all-provinces coordinated

rice breeding program will be designated with numbers prefixed by Taikeng (japonica) or Taisen (indica), commencing with the yield trials in 1986. No new varieties will be released by individual rice breeding stations. *ℳ*

Amir Khan/international Inventor

Amir U. Khan, head of IRRI's Agricultural Engineering Department, received the International Inventors Award (IIA) for Industry 13 Jun 1986 in Stockholm. The award, modeled after the Nobel Prize, was presented by H.M. King Carl Gustaf of Sweden.

Sweden instituted the IIA to recognize outstanding innovations in water, forestry, and industry. Dr. Khan received the prestigious award for his contributions toward developing the farm machinery industry in developing nations. One of his inventions, the axial-flow thresher, is being produced in eight Asian countries, where local manufacture has generated substantial employment. *ℳ*

Other IRRI scientists recognized

Also honored by the Swedish Inventor's Association on 14 Jun in Stockholm were Yong Woon Jeon, Leonides S. Halos, and Clarence W. Bockhop, IRRI Agricultural Engineering Department. Their innovation, warehouse dryer using nonconventional energy sources, received an honorable mention diploma and the Swedish Inventor's Association plaque in the energy field. *ℳ*

Classic soils work recognized

The Institute for Scientific Information selected a paper by Dennis J. Greenland, deputy director general, as the Citation Classic for the 2 Jun 1986 issue of *Current contents: agriculture, biology and environmental sciences*. His paper, Interaction between clays and organic compounds in soils. Part II. Adsorption of soil organic compounds and its effect on soil properties, was first published in *Soils Fert.* 28:521-532, 1965. A Citation Classic is a highly cited publication as identified by Science Citation Index. *ℳ*